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Types of Public-Private Partnership Management Mechanisms

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Abstract: *This article examines the main concepts and practical correctness of the corporate governance mechanism within the framework of Public Private Partnership (PPP). Public-private partnership is a mechanism aimed at solving social and economic problems by pooling resources, knowledge and skills between the public and private sectors. The article analyzes the important aspects of corporate management, such as strategic planning, assignment of responsibilities, management structure and financial mechanisms.*

Also, based on international experiences, we offer concrete strategies and mechanisms to increase the effectiveness of the public-private partnership this analysis helps to ensure effective management in cooperation between the public and private sectors.

Key words: *Public-Private Partnership (PPP). Corporate governance. efficiency. Risk management.*

Public-private partnership is an effective form of cooperation between the public and private sectors, which jointly pool resources for the implementation of specific projects. Public-private partnership projects play an important role in achieving the country's development goals, especially in infrastructure, education, health and other important sectors.

1. Development of infrastructure: through public-private partnership projects, the state will have the opportunity to attract the financial and technical resources of the private sector and build and modernize important infrastructure facilities such as roads, bridges, energy facilities.

2. Stimulate economic growth: Public-private partnership projects help create new jobs, develop the local economy, and attract investment.
3. Improving the quality of services: Through public-private partnership projects, the state will have the opportunity to provide quality and efficient services to the population. For example, the participation of the private sector in the health sector helps improve the quality of hospitals and services for patients.
4. Reducing the financial burden of the government: Public-private partnership projects help to reduce the financial burden of the government, because the private sector participates in the financing of the project.
5. Development of innovations: Public-private partnership projects provide an opportunity to attract innovative ideas and technologies from the private sector.

In order to achieve success in public-private partnership development management, the following factors must be taken into account:

1. Transparency and Accountability: Public-Private Partnership projects should be transparent and accountable, as this will help build public trust and reduce the risk of corruption.
2. Legal framework: There should be a clear legal framework governing PPP projects.
3. Independent monitoring: Independent monitoring of the implementation of public-private partnership projects is necessary.
4. Public participation: Public participation is important in the implementation of public-private partnership projects.
5. Cooperation between the public and private sectors: Cooperation between the public and private sectors is important for the successful implementation of public-private partnership projects. Public-private partnership is an important mechanism for ensuring cooperation between the state and the private sector in the economy. In this article, the main concepts, principles and practical correctness of the mechanism of corporate governance in public-private partnership are considered.

Public-private partnerships aim to solve social and economic problems by combining the resources, knowledge and skills of the public and private sectors. Through this mechanism, efficiency is increased in infrastructure projects, services and other areas.

Corporate management is a mechanism designed to effectively organize the economic activities of companies, define strategies, make decisions and allocate resources. Clarifying tasks of the corporate governance mechanism in public-private partnership:

Strategic Planning: Development of long-term strategies for the implementation of public-private partnership projects.

Defining Responsibilities: Clearly defining the mutual obligations and rights of both parties.

Creating Visibility: Identifying sources of tangible benefits, i.e. returns and benefits, for owners and investors.

In public private partnership projects, the corporate governance structure is important to ensure effective cooperation between the public and private sectors. This structure usually consists of:

Community of partners: A compromise between the public and private sectors involved in the project.
Assigning Authority: The authority providing strategic management of the project, such as a public institution or a private company.

Support groups: Experts, engineers, etc., who monitor and support the implementation of the project.

Financial mechanisms are important for implementation of public private partnership. These include:

Attracting investment: Finding sources of financing from the private sector.

State subsidies: Funds allocated by the state to support projects. Financial instruments: Use of bonds, loans and other financial instruments.

Successful examples of public private partnerships are infrastructure projects in the UK, Australia and the USA. In public-private partnership, the corporate governance mechanism serves to effectively organize cooperation between the state and the private sector. Through this mechanism, efficiency, priorities and financial stability of projects are ensured. Clear strategies, proper management structure and effective financial mechanisms are essential for success in this field.

The principles and mechanisms presented in this article can be useful for improving corporate governance in the field of public private partnership.

In conclusion, Public-Private Partnership is an important factor in development management, which helps to achieve the development goals of the country. However, it is necessary to take into account the above factors when implementing PPP projects.

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